

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF UNITS AND RITUAL OF COMPLIMENT AS UNIT OF SPEECH ETIQUETTE

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Annotation. *Etiquette is a set of rules of conduct that regulate the external manifestation human relationships (treatment with others, forms of address and greetings, behavior in public places, manners and dress). Etiquette is an integral part of the external human culture and society. It includes those requirements that acquire the character more or less strictly regulated ceremonial and in the observance of which has a special meaning a certain form of behavior.*

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Etiquette is a French concept and its appearance is associated with the rule behavior of invited guests, described on special cards (in French Etiquette - label). The word is translated from French as "established order of conduct". It is noteworthy that modern the French observe the rules of etiquette and are as strict as the courtier etiquette in the royal era of France. French business etiquette requires a lot of formalities.

Any act of communication has a beginning, main part and final. If the addressee is unfamiliar to the subject of speech, then communication begins with an acquaintance.

In this case, it can occur directly and indirectly. According to the rules of good manners, it is not customary to enter into a conversation with a stranger and introduce yourself.

However, there are times when this needs to be done. To attract someone's attention to themselves in French and Russian is enough deal with the words:

- Sorry! - Pardon! Sorry! - Excusez-moi!

In French in this situation, referring to a stranger, you can also say:

- Pardon! Excusez-moi! Voulez-vous m'excuser?

In addition, it should be noted that Pardon! more neutral than two subsequent appeals.

- Excusez-moi! - Voulez-vous m'excuser, two whose most polite form is Voulez-vous m'excuser, who foreigners are not recommended to use.

The following degree of politeness when focusing attention:

- Sorry to bother you - Excusez-moi de vous deranger.

- Sorry to bother you. - Excusez-moi du dèrangement.

A polite form of asking a stranger is neutral:

- Tell me, please... Pouvez-vous me dire....

This form of question also makes it possible to ask where the place or institution you need is located, is it possible and how pass (pass).

- Excuse me, could you tell me where it is..

- Pardon, pourriez-vous me dire où se trouve....

Turning to an outsider and asking questions:

- Excuse me, you don't know...? - Pardon, vous ne savez pas...

- Excuse me, would you say...? - Pouvez-vous me dire?

The questioner not only intends to obtain the necessary information, but also shows a certain degree of upbringing: more high in phrases - Pourriez-vous me dire... - Excusez-moi, ne pourriez-vous me dire..., less high - a phrase where there is no inversion of the verb in interrogative form - Pardon, vous ne savez pas..

Therefore, a foreigner must apply to one or another people selectively, given the different levels of their education.

If you want to get a more kind answer, you can use the following forms,

How: -Please...- Soyez gentil (le), ayez l'obligenccede + infinitive

-Be kind... -Ayez l'amabilité de + infinitive...

A somewhat more formal question is: Would you kindly say?

- Vous seriez amiable de me dire?

This official shade is retained in the French equivalent.

Along with this question form, there are neutral ones:

-You can't (say)...? - Ne pouvez-vous dire...?

Neutral, but more polite replicas look:

-Could you...? - Ne pourriez-vous pas (me dire)?

- Is it easy for you...? -Vous est-il possible de+ infinitive...?

It sounds emphatically intelligent: it won't make it difficult for you to say ..

Pourriez- vous me dire, s'il vous plait...?

The way to get attention is to ask:

- May I ask you? - Puis jevous demander...

- May I ask you a question? - Je peux vous poser une question?

Much more common in French are questions of the form Puis-je vous demander..?

than Je peux vous poser une question? although they are sufficient are neutral.

Neutrality is sufficiently manifested in

handling: - Can I have you (you) for a minute?

- Je peux vous (te) parler un moment?

When the conversation ends, the interlocutors use the formula

breakups, breakups. They wish:

All the best (good) to you! Bonne Chance!

Be healthy! Portez vous bien! Happily! Bon courage!

In an official setting, stereotypes are often used:

Allow me to say goodbye! Let me say goodbye!

Permettez-moi de faire mes adieux!

When saying goodbye, shorter, more colloquial forms emphasizing that the speakers are parting for a short time: Everything!

Abientôt - see you soon Bye! Atout à l'heure! Hello! Salut!

Saying goodbye for a while, the interlocutors can exchange such phrases,

How: I don't say goodbye to you! Je ne vous dis pas au revoir!

We don't say goodbye! Nous reviendrons vous voir!

We'll see you again! On se retrouvons vous voir!

I'll see you again! Je vous reverrai, my!

Thus, it can be concluded that when teaching speech etiquette should pay attention to the formation of cultural literacy of students and at the same time it is important to select the speech and language material according to the needs and possibilities students, with real speech situations of their potential communication.

A tactfully and timely compliment, he raises the mood of the addressee, sets up a positive attitude towards opponent. A compliment is said at the beginning of a conversation, at a meeting, acquaintance or during a conversation, at parting. Compliment always pleasant. Only an insincere compliment is dangerous, a compliment for the sake of a compliment, an overly enthusiastic compliment.

A compliment is a short expression of respect and friendship that we address to the interlocutor. The purpose of a compliment is to convince the interlocutor that our heartfelt feelings correlate with verbal expression, with the intention to win him over. But it must also be taken into account that there is two dangerous extremes in a compliment and one must be able to adhere to golden mean. A compliment, first of all, should emphasize those qualities of a person that are appropriate to mention and specific circumstances, also taking into account the very subject of the conversation.

The compliment refers to the appearance, indicates the excellent professional abilities of the addressee, the professional abilities of the addressee, his high morality, gives an overall positive assessment:

You look good (excellent, fine).

Vous avez bonne mine (l'air si jeune)

. You look good today! Vouz avez tres bonne mine!

The object of a compliment is often one of the positive qualities of the interlocutor, denoted by a brief or complete adjective in Russian.

French expresses these compliments with adjectives *très*, if it is necessary to emphasize any quality, nouns with adjective evaluation - for example:

-This is an exceptionally beautiful woman! C'est une femme d'une grande beauté!

You are smart and beautiful! Vous êtes intelligente, belle!

If the speaker seeks to emphasize some external characteristics, features of the character or behavior of the interlocutor, he uses adverbs *très* very much, as well as the adjective *ce* what:

You are very smart! Vous êtes très intelligent!

How smart you are! Vous êtes si intelligent!

How smart you are! Que (comme) vous êtes intelligent!

A professional assessment is also a compliment interlocutor, while using both Russian and French evaluative adjectives *bon* good, *beau* beautiful (*bon*, *excellent*, and also *de grande classe*):

You are such a good specialist, a wonderful teacher.

Vous êtes un bon spécialiste, un très bon professeur.

When evaluating the interlocutor in terms of his professional qualities the Russian language uses the adverb *très* very and adjectives *ce* what and *tel* such, French - the adverb *très*, the intensifying particle *si* and the adjective *bon*, as well as the verb *être* or *faire*.

You are a very good translator! Vous êtes un très bon traducteur!

You are such a good translator! Vous êtes un si bon traducteur!

What a good translator you are! Quel bon traducteur vous êtes!

Compliments about appearance, clothes, hairstyles, elegance is done more often by women than men:

A short haircut makes you look younger. Ces cheveux courts vous rajeunissent.

This suit makes you look younger. Ce costume vous rajeunit (va bien).

The present tense is also used in professional evaluation and is introduced by adverbs good, excellent, excellent, excellent: we translate well, sing beautifully, dance wonderfully.

Vous traduisez bien, chantez tres bien, dansez admirablement.

The object of evaluation can be a good character, a sharp mind, fine taste, good sense of humor:

You have a good character (soft, kind, flexible). Vous avez un bon caractère (un caractère doux, un caractère accomodant.)

You have a sharp, penetrating mind, subtle, critical. Vous avez un sprint vif, clairvoyant, perspicace, fin, critique.

Do you have a good sense of humor. Votre humor très fin.

A compliment is a positive assessment of the interlocutor from the point of view of his manner of communicating with others; assessment may concern characteristics of the character or degree of ability to communicate:

Swami is interesting to talk to. Il est intèressant de vous frequenter.

It's nice to talk with you. Il est agreable de vous parler.

The response to the compliment contains a brief expression of gratitude:

Thank you! Mercy!

Thanks for the compliment! Merci pourle compliment!

The response of a polite person should also contain evaluative gratitude or approval for a compliment.

French the range of gratitude for a compliment includes adjectives content, heureux, enchante, suggests the use of infinitives or complex sentences.

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